

Personal Data Stores and the GDPR's lawful grounds for processing personal data

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Abstract

Personal Data Stores ('PDSs') entail users having a (physical or virtual) device within which they themselves can, in theory, capture, aggregate, and control the access to and the transfer of personal data. Their aim is to empower users in relation to their personal data, strengthening their opportunities for data protection, privacy, and/or to facilitate trade and monetisation. As PDS technologies develop, it is important to consider their role in relation to issues of data protection. The General Data Protection Regulation requires that the processing of user data be predicated on one of its defined lawful bases, whereby the Regulation does not favour any one basis over another. We explore how PDS architectures relate to these lawful bases, and observe that they tend to favour the bases that require direct user involvement. This paper considers issues that the envisaged architectural choices surrounding the lawful grounds may entail.

Keywords privacy; data protection; lawful grounds for processing; decentralisation; personal data stores; control; transparency

1. Introduction

Online services typically collect, store and perform computations on users' personal data, though their operations are largely opaque. Users may struggle to understand, let alone control how applications, services and devices work; how their data is captured, analysed or transferred; and why, by whom or where it is being stored.¹

This has led to the development of alternative technical data processing architectures. In essence, *Personal Data Stores* ('PDSs') provide users with a (physical or virtual) device² that aims at allowing users themselves to capture, aggregate, and control the processing, access to and transfer of their personal data. In this way, instead of the data being

brought to service providers for 'centralised' processing *en masse*, decisions for data transfer, and indeed, the processing itself, is 'decentralised', i.e. performed on the user's device.

PDSs seek to address issues around transparency and user control intrinsic to centralised approaches to data processing – which often entail information and power asymmetries between users and (usually large) companies that process their data. PDS advocates argue that the technology, in tackling user control issues, could reshape the data economy and the trust relationships among citizens, governments and companies.³

PDSs are *platforms* (as they mediate between users and those seeking to process their data) that aim to give individuals control over the management of their data. Some examples of PDSs at various stages of development include Databox, Mydex CIC, MyData, the Hub of All Things and Solid (developed by Tim Berners Lee).⁴ PDSs represent a nascent technology, purporting an alternative approach for data management.

Given that PDS architectures, by definition, involve the processing of personal data, the EU's *General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)*⁵ must be complied with by the relevant parties involved in undertaking that processing whenever EU law applies. The GDPR requires transparent, fair and lawful processing of personal data, which must be predicated on a defined lawful basis (see Articles 6 and 9 GDPR, and the discussion in §4).⁶ Processing will otherwise be unlawful. The processing of '*special categories*' of personal data, which could pose significant risks to an individual's rights and freedoms (where it reveals, e.g., ethnicity, political opinion, religious belief, health or sexual orientation), is prohibited unless the user has *explicitly* consented, or under a number of other strict conditions (Art. 9 (2) GDPR).

In light of these legal requirements, this paper considers how PDSs - given their key aim to increase levels of user empowerment - relate to the lawful bases of data processing.

2. Decentralised data processing

PDSs envision a data processing ecosystem which better equips users with visibility and control over (a) the data captured and stored by their PDS; (b) how this data can be processed and (c) how the data and/or the results of this processing can be accessed by or transferred to third party services.

By localising data an individual's data and processing to their device, PDSs seek to provide an alternative to the current centralised models of data processing - where data is often transferred, aggregated and computation performed in environments over which users have limited knowledge and visibility, let alone control.

2.1 PDS architectures

Users create personal information in many ways – including by sensors, by their actions and activities, manually, etc. In a PDS ecosystem, user data is local to their PDS device.

Data within a PDS is processed (and transferred) by way of *apps*.⁷ These are somewhat analogous to mobile apps for smartphones. Some apps might operate locally on the device, without external data transfer, while other apps might conduct activities that transfer data (stored, computed or real-time) from the device, while others perform computations over user data, sending back results to the relevant (defined) entity.

In a PDS context, apps typically operate in a more constrained technical environment. This at a minimum controls the data that is released; and the apps must specify the types and data and processing they will undertake.⁸ Some PDS platforms aim to monitor, make visible, and constrain app behaviour, as well as to provide an intervention point and mediate the interactions (data exchanges) between the users and the app developer.

Specifically, regarding *transparency*, PDSs generally provide information to users through notices and alerts about what data the app wants to access, and how that data will be processed⁹, and about (automatic or manual) risk assessments¹⁰, both before installation. Some aim at providing operational (run-time) logs, audits, visualisations and alerts. PDSs also seek to give users *control*, not only by giving more detail regarding the apps they install¹¹, but also through mechanisms that allow users to define what apps may do with their data (e.g. the data sources an app can access¹²). The platforms

generally maintain mechanisms to ensure that app behaviour (including data processing and transfer) are properly constrained in line with user preferences, and the developer-defined behaviours.

2.2 Purported benefits from PDSs

Platforms purport a range of benefits. Those relating to data protection include:

- user control over data capture¹³;
- that user consent becomes ‘real’ (as it is no longer a ‘box-ticking’ exercise)¹⁴ and better informed (through logs, audits, permanent monitoring of processing and visualisations)¹⁵;
- that data, including ‘sensitive’ data, will be protected from access by app developers¹⁶;
- isolated storage of user data and apps, to prevent apps from unobtrusively interacting with raw user data without user agreement¹⁷;
- improved adherence with the data protection principles of purpose limitation and data minimisation, as data access and usages must be clearly defined and permitted¹⁸; and
- generally incentivising app developers towards taking more privacy friendly approaches.¹⁹

The benefits for app developers described by PDS platform include: (i) access to ‘richer data sets’²⁰, where app developers could ‘gain insights in user data that would otherwise not be possible’²¹ given users may more willing to provide access to data if transfers are more visible, defined or restricted transfers, and/or by allowing on-device processing if only the computed results (which may be less sensitive) are returned; and (ii) reducing data acquisition and management costs, as the data is captured by users²², and security, as data resides in the users’ PDSs, not the organisation’s ecosystem²³.

3. Systemic privacy issues & PDSs

A key issue regarding current online services is the information asymmetries between users and the organisations processing their data. These stem from the fact that users often lack knowledge or understanding of (i) the practices of the organisations capturing and processing their data; (ii) the technical specifics of the architecture they are dealing with, (iii) the data sharing arrangements of those third parties, and (iv) the associated (data, and often surveillance-driven) business models. Moreover, the analytics inherent in these practices

mean that organisations can generate further insights into users' behaviour and interests, amplifying these asymmetries.

The stated goal of PDS platforms is user empowerment through the architecture and audit- and visibility-measures. Through these measures, PDSs aim at increasing levels of transparency and control. In line with the goal for user empowerment, in §4.1 we consider how PDSs lend themselves to consent or contract-based grounds for personal data processing. However, we note that these grounds for processing have well-identified problems around information asymmetries and therefore with obtaining properly informed consent and contractual agreement from users.²⁴ Though the technical measures implemented in PDSs might assist with some aspects, issues regarding '*privacy self-management*'²⁵ remain, given that users are ultimately tasked and largely responsible for protecting their own privacy, regardless of the systemic issues at play.

3.1 Transparency of processing

The largely opaque nature of data processing often results in such power and information asymmetries between users and third parties.²⁶ As discussed, even knowledgeable users are likely to struggle to make informed data protection decisions. PDS platforms typically claim some form of active user agreement with notices prior to installation of apps, the checking of apps for privacy risks, and logging, monitoring and visualising app behaviour will inform users about what happens to their data. Based on that information, users might take better informed decisions about whether to engage or indeed, disengage with an app. While the measures that PDSs envisage may assist in helping users understand to some extent what happens in their PDSs, simply informing users about what data will be processed, in what way, and for what purposes may not be sufficient to address the systemic issues around information asymmetries as just discussed.

3.2 Users often lack technical expertise

Beyond the lack of transparency over processing, an important concern that should also be addressed is that effectively informing users highly depends on a user's technical IT-skills and cognitive ability. An app's or platform's explanations and visualisations of data flows may be extremely complex and

difficult to understand for non-experts. One could also question whether giving yet more information and more choice about complex and difficult to understand aspects of data processing, like predictive analytics, is the best approach.

Users will likely require some tech expertise and knowledge to meaningfully interrogate, control and understand the processing. Platforms should consider how to make any transparency measures efficient, real and effective. As PDS platforms are still developing, there are opportunities to improve user support with e.g. default policies or usage of templates.

3.3 Visibility & control after transfer

Informing users at a level matching their technical understanding may in some cases assist in addressing issues regarding information asymmetries. However, neither a user nor a platform has effective means to understand or exercise control over what happens to the data *after* it has been transferred beyond the PDS infrastructure.²⁷ Concerns regarding the handling of user data after it is transferred is a general problem, relevant for both centralised and decentralised processing environments. Risks arise from the fact that once data moves beyond a boundary, its usage is essentially out of sight. Such risks could include, for example, secondary uses of data a user would not have agreed with (e.g. undisclosed monetisation²⁸), or where unexpected or undesired inferences or profiling occurs, which could be used to influence, nudge or manipulate.²⁹

PDSs generally do not purport to address these concerns; however, they may assist by enabling users to be both better informed, and have greater control over what data is transferred. There are opportunities to explore legal, technical and other measures towards addressing privacy and data management issues after the point of transfer.³⁰

4. Lawful processing in PDSs

While PDSs raise interesting considerations from a broader perspective of systemic privacy issues, the choices in PDS architecture regarding the lawful grounds for processing also merit separate considerations from a GDPR perspective. The GDPR requires that a data *controller* decides the lawful basis for processing personal data (Article

5(1)(a) GDPR).³¹ Several grounds exist; those most relevant to our discussion are:

- a. *consent* (Article 6(1)(a) GDPR), or, in some circumstances, *explicit consent* (Article 9(2)(a));
- b. where processing is necessary for the performance of a *contract* to which the data subject is party or in order to take steps at the request of the data subject prior to entering into a contract (Article 6 (1)(b) GDPR);
- c. where processing is necessary in the performance of a task carried out in the *public interest* or in the exercise of official authority vested in the controller (Article 6 (1)(e) GDPR), or for reasons of substantial public interest (Article 9 (2)(g)), or
- d. where processing is necessary for the *legitimate interests* of the controller or by a third party (Article 6 (1)(f) GDPR).

The GDPR does not favour any one basis over another. Further, in relation to a particular application, several distinct grounds may be appropriate for different aspects of processing. Each ground has different requirements, some of which (e.g. c and d, above) require a balancing between the interest being pursued and the fundamental rights of the data subject. Which basis is most appropriate will depend on the specific purpose and contexts for use and the nature of the parties involved and their relationships; for example, some grounds will be unavailable to commercial actors, while public bodies are often unable to rely on consent as a ground³² (due to the power imbalances between individuals and public bodies).

While in practice PDS ecosystems can involve a number of stakeholders who might be controllers in certain contexts, our discussion focuses on app developers, considering them as data controllers that leverage the PDS to process a user's personal data for the purposes they have defined.³³

4.1 Consent and contract

PDS platforms tend to align their architecture with the grounds that require user involvement. 'Consent' as a lawful ground must be *informed, specific* and *freely given* by a user. 'Informed' means that controllers provide users with information so users can make informed decisions and understand what they agree to.³⁴ 'Freely given' implies real user choice and control.³⁵ 'Specific' requires that the purposes are clear and well-defined, and that choice

exists in relation to each of them.³⁶ *Explicit* consent is, in most commercial contexts, required whenever the controller intends to process special categories of personal data.³⁷ Explicit consent is also one of the available grounds whenever the controller intends to apply solely automated decision-making based on personal data where that decision-making has legal or similarly significant effects.³⁸

Related is the ground where processing is necessary for the performance of a *contract* to which the user is a party, or in order to take steps necessary to enter into a contract.³⁹ Note there appears issues with app developers with relying on contract as a processing ground, unless they require something other than the user's personal data in exchange for the service.⁴⁰

As §2 sets out, a key aim of PDSs is to provide means for users to be better informed, and thereby - in theory - better positioned to give (and maintain) consent for processing or to enter into a contract.⁴¹ At the same time, installing apps for that processing, as well as configuring data usage preferences and policies to enable such processing, means that active actions from the user are needed for processing to occur. In this way, PDS platforms, by requiring such user involvement, seem to be oriented towards supporting consent and contract-based processing.

While we recognise that PDSs might help assist users in understanding (to some extent) what happens in their PDSs, the architectural measures described in §2.1 are likely not sufficient to address the systemic information asymmetries discussed in §3. At first sight, requiring user involvement might appear to bring about user empowerment. Yet, the systemic privacy issues may work to diminish the *informed* character of any consent or contractual agreement.

4.2 Legitimate interests & public task

Less considered in a PDS context are the grounds that are *not* based on specific user agreement.

The *legitimate interest* basis requires the controller to demonstrate that the processing of an individual's data is necessary for a specific, legitimate purpose. The controller must balance their interests (e.g. regarding their business) with the individual's rights (particularly privacy and data protection rights, but also other relevant rights). The controller must be in a position to justify their position, as well as inform users in a transparent

manner.⁴² Also relevant is where processing is necessary for the performance of a *task* carried out in the *public interest*, where the task or the controller's authority has a clear foundation in law.

As discussed, PDS platforms are designed for user involvement: having mechanisms to help a user decide what to install, set their data preferences, constraints, etc. That is, PDS platforms generally predicate processing on user action. It is therefore unclear how, in operational terms, this reconciles with the lawful processing bases that do *not* require user involvement, or where user preferences might not align with the controller's legitimate interest or a task in the public interest. This appears one area for further consideration.

That said, mechanisms provided by PDS platforms can be reused to assist these grounds in various ways. Transparency of information, such as the nature of the legitimate interests or the legal basis for processing, can be presented to users through similar means used to present other app-related information to users, etc. Moreover, these grounds include the right for an individual to object to such processing.⁴³ Aside from uninstallation of the relevant apps, one can envisage a PDS's consent management mechanisms to be repurposed to give effect to an individual's objection. Though as the right to object is not necessarily absolute, how PDSs implement this requires consideration.⁴⁴

4.3 Special category data

The GDPR classifies certain data as *special category*: data considered particularly sensitive and requiring more stringent protection and management.⁴⁵ PDSs envisage storing a broad range of an individual's data and will likely entail capturing a broad range of sensitive information.

Processing special category data is prohibited by Article 9 GDPR unless an exemption applies; in a commercial context, this is often explicit consent. App developers processing special category data must therefore ensure that the consent (or other relevant requirements) are met. PDSs often purport to assist this; as part of their user empowerment aims, PDS platforms claim mechanisms to improve, facilitate and make consent processes more explicit and informed, while at the same time, providing the infrastructure for securing data from unauthorised and inappropriate access – which is important where data is sensitive.

Identifying special category data has its challenges. While some data will clearly fall within a special category, there will often be situations where seemingly innocuous data can reveal information falling into one of those special categories. For instance, when data acts as a proxy, e.g. where a postcode might imply race⁴⁶; or where certain benign data can be combined with other data to become particularly revealing.⁴⁷ Therefore, it has been argued that in practice there is the potential for all personal data to, in effect, become special category.⁴⁸ This is particularly relevant in a PDS context, which may mean that a prudent app developer should treat all data as if it is special category. This is because of the nature of a PDS, which holds a great wealth of personal data, and where the processing happens on device without the app developer necessarily 'knowing' the nature of all the data and associated contexts involved in processing.

Again, PDSs may provide the tooling to assist these aspects. As consent is a key focus of PDS platforms, the mechanisms offered should be designed to facilitate obtaining explicit consent for such processing. Some argue that the PDS can place extra constraints over special category data⁴⁹, though this brings practical challenges given the difficulties in identifying such data.

An interesting consideration is whether the data access and processing constraints that a PDS platform provides can be used by controllers to mitigate and minimise their risks. That is, by the app developer (through processing policies, manifests, etc) being able to specify, at a granular level, the data they are interested in, they also in effect define the types of data that they do *not* wish to process. In other words, an app developer can specify their *own* constraints regarding the data they are willing to process, which the platform enforces. Whether and how controllers use a PDS's technical infrastructure to proactively mitigate their own risk exposure and compliance requirements remains to be seen.

5. Concluding remarks

PDSs propose decentralised technical architectures as a means for empowering users regarding their data. Though PDSs might assist by increasing levels of transparency and control, the more systemic privacy issues will likely remain. Generally, PDS architectures seem to be designed to support active user involvement, which in terms of the legal

grounds for processing seems best to align with those of consent and contract. How the other lawful grounds practically reconcile with the operations of PDSs appears an area for further investigation.

¹ See eg. P. Tolmie et al, 'This has to be the cats - personal data legibility in networked sensing systems', (2016) Proceedings of the 19th ACM Conference on Computer-Supported Cooperative Work and Social Computing <http://www.cs.nott.ac.uk/~pszaxc/work/CSCW_1_2016.pdf> accessed 21 May 2019.

² A. Crabtree et al, 'Building Accountability into the Internet of Things: the IoT databox Model' (2018) 4 Journal of Reliable Intelligent Environments, 39.

³ EDPS 'Opinion 9/2016 on Personal Information Management Systems. Towards more user empowerment in managing and processing personal data' (20 October 2016); Crabtree et al (n 2) 39; L. Urquhart et al, 'Demonstrably doing accountability in the Internet of Things' (2018) 80 International Journal of Law and Information Technology, 1; N. Anciaux et al, 'Personal Data Management Systems: The security and functionality standpoint' (2019) 80 Information Systems, 13; Royal Society Report, 'Protecting privacy in practice: The current use, development and limits of Privacy Enhancing Technologies in data analysis report' (March 2019).

⁴ See <<http://iotdatabox.com>>; <<https://mydex.org>>; <<https://mydata.org/mydata-101/>>; <hubofallthings.com>; <<https://solid.inrupt.com>>; accessed 20 April 2019.

⁵ Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46 (General data Protection Regulation), OJ 2016 L 119/1.

⁶ Article 5 (1) (a) GDPR.

⁷ Note that the terminology varies by platform. Not all platforms would describe processing as occurring through apps, though there tends to be some form of conceptually similar construct.

⁸ Crabtree et al (n 2) 47, Urquhart et al (n 3) 17.

⁹ Crabtree et al (n 2) 47.

¹⁰ Crabtree et al (n 2) 45-46; HAT Data Exchange Rating Scheme, 1-2 <<https://www.hatcommunity.org/hat-dex-rating>> accessed 15 April 2019.

¹¹ Urquhart et al (n 3) 21; eg Databox envisages high risks whenever apps export personal data outside the EU, or when apps access 'sensitive information'; low risks would emerge whenever results from computation are not transferred.

¹² Crabtree et al (n 2) 47.

¹³ Digi.me: 'Only you decide whether to share data with apps for benefits and personal insights', <<https://digi.me>>.

¹⁴ Crabtree et al (n 2) 43.

¹⁵ A. Eskola et al, 'MyData, A Nordic Model for human-centred personal data management', 3 <<http://julkaisut.valtioneuvo.fi/handle/10024/78439>> accessed 16 April 2019.

¹⁶ Crabtree et al (n 2) 46; T. Lodge et al, 'Developing GDPR compliant apps for the edge', Proceedings of the 13th International Workshop on Data Privacy Management (Barcelona Springer 2018) 313.

¹⁷ Crabtree et al (n 2) 43.

¹⁸ Crabtree et al (n 2) 40, 47; Urquhart et al (n 3) 16.

¹⁹ Crabtree et al (n 2) 45.

²⁰ Eskola et al (n 15) 3; Digi.me <<https://digi.me>>; Citizen.me <<https://www.citizenme.com/public/wp/business/>> accessed 24 January 2019.

²¹ I. Ng, The Market for Person-controlled Personal Data with the Hub-of-all-Things (HAT), WMG Service Systems Research Group, Working Paper Series, Issue nr. 1/18, 26; Cozy at <<https://cozy.io/en/business/>> (accessed 24 January 2019).

²² Eskola et al (n 15) 4.

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²³ Crabtree et al (n 2) 23.

²⁴ D. Solove, 'Privacy Self-Management and the Consent Dilemma' (2013), 126 Harvard Law Review 1880.

²⁵ Solove (n 23) 1880.

²⁶ A. Mantelero, 'Social Control, Transparency, and Participation in the Big Data World' (2014) Journal of Internet Law, 23-29.

²⁷ J. Singh et al, 'Big ideas paper: Policy-driven middleware for a legally-compliant Internet of Things' (12 December 2016) <<https://dl.acm.org/citation.cfm?id=2988349>>; Crabtree et al (n 2) 51; J. Singh et al, 'Decision Provenance: Harnessing Data Flow for Accountable Systems', IEEE Access, vol. 7 (2019) 6562.

²⁸ See eg C. Silverman et al, 'Popular Apps In Google's Play Store Are Abusing Permissions And Committing Ad Fraud' BuzzFeed (14 April 2019).

<<https://www.buzzfeednews.com/article/craigsilverman/google-play-store-ad-fraud-du-group-baidu>> accessed 19 April 2019.

²⁹ S. Wachter et al, 'A Right to Reasonable Inferences: Re-Thinking Data Protection Law in the Age of Big Data and AI' (2019) Columbia Business Law Review 1.

³⁰ See eg Singh et al (n 27, 2019).

³¹ Article 4 (7) and Article 5 (2) GDPR.

³² Recital 43 GDPR.

³³ See e.g. Crabtree et al (n 2) 43; Mydata, 'Declaration of Mydata principles', <<https://mydata.org/declaration/>>; Mydex Charter, <<https://dev.mydex.org/mydex-charter.html>> accessed 18 April 2019. Given the range of PDS ecosystems, and given that PDSs are currently largely under development, assignments of 'controllers' or 'processors' may vary by platform and are yet to be settled.

³⁴ Article 29 Working Party, 'Guidelines on consent under Regulation 2016/679' (WP 259, 10 April 2018) 13.

³⁵ Article 29 Working Party (n 34) 5. If consent is e.g. bundled up as a non-negotiable part of terms and conditions it is presumed not to have been freely given.

³⁶ Article 29 Working Party (n 34) 11.

³⁷ Article 9 (1)(a) GDPR.

³⁸ Article 22 (2)(c) GDPR.

³⁹ Contracts between companies and PDS users are used in the ecosystem of e.g. HAT, see 'HATDeX Platform Guide', section 'legal' <<https://hatdex.org/>> accessed 19 April 2019.

⁴⁰ Whether personal data can be offered as a contractual obligation (i.e. as consideration) is currently unclear (see Langhanke et al, 'Consumer Data as Consideration' (2015) 4 Journal of European Consumer and Market Law), though a proposed EU directive would allow this in some circumstances (see COM/2015/0634 final). In the interim, app developers should perhaps only rely on contract as a lawful basis where the counter-performance is something other than the processing of the users' personal data (e.g., payment for the service).

⁴¹ Note the discussion of §3 regarding systemic issues.

⁴² Articles 13 (1)(d) and 14 (2)(b) GDPR.

⁴³ Article 21 (1) GDPR.

⁴⁴ Article 21 (1), (6) GDPR.

⁴⁵ Article 9 (1)(a), Recital 51 GDPR.

⁴⁶ A. Datta et al, 'Proxy Discrimination in Data Driven Systems: Theory and Experiments with Machine Learnt Data' (25 July 2017) <<https://arxiv.org/pdf/1707.08120.pdf>>.

⁴⁷ For examples M. Fazlioglu, 'Beyond the Nature of data: Obstacles to Protecting Sensitive Information in the European Union and the United States' (2019) 46 Fordham Urban Law Journal 271.

⁴⁸ Fazlioglu (n 47) 295.

⁴⁹ Lodge et al (n 16).